

Should Flexible Mixed Polyolefins Be Sent to Mechanical or Chemical Recycling? A Technology-Agnostic Analysis Based on a Sustainability–Circularity Index.

Merel Molenbuur^{1#}, Cris Garcia-Saravia Ortiz-de-Montellano^{1,2#}, Steven De Meester^{1,3}, Yvonne van der Meer², Milad Golkaram¹ and Kim Ragaert^{1*}

¹ *Circular Plastics, Department of Circular Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Science and Engineering, Maastricht University, PO Box 616, 6200 MD Maastricht, The Netherlands*

² *Faculty of Science and Engineering, Aachen Maastricht Institute for Biobased Materials, Maastricht University, Brightlands Chemelot Campus, Urmonderbaan 22, 6167 RD, Geleen, The Netherlands*

³ *Laboratory for Circular Process Engineering (LCPE), Department of Green Chemistry and Technology, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, Ghent University, Graaf Karel de Goedelaan 5, B-8500 Kortrijk, Belgium*

These authors contributed equally to this work.

* Corresponding author. E-mail: k.ragaert@maastrichtuniversity.nl

Abstract Flexible mixed polyolefins (fMPO) represent a significant portion of post-household plastic packaging waste, which is currently—at best—recycled into durable, thick-walled products via mechanical recycling (MR). However, the upcoming chemical recycling (CR) pathway of pyrolysis is highly suitable for fMPO, which may cause future feedstock conflicts. In this work, the availability of fMPO in 2030 across three scenarios with various potential allocations to MR and CR is assessed. The findings for all three scenarios show insufficient fMPO to satisfy the 2030 demands of both MR and CR, even if the available feedstock for recycling increases by 25% and the (mass-balanced as fuel-exempt) pyrolysis efficiency reaches 90%. Life-cycle assessments and the Product Circularity Indicator are applied from a product perspective, using a thick-walled bench and flexible packaging as representative case studies for MR and CR, respectively. The results are integrated into a Sustainability–Circularity Index (SCI)—a novel metric that reflects the circularity gained per euro of environmental cost for a given functional unit. In terms of sustainability, MR consistently delivers lower environmental impacts and higher circularity, with mechanically recycled benches outperforming benches made of both virgin high-density polyethylene (HDPE) and cast iron, and performing on par with benches made of sustainably sourced wood. Although CR enables food-grade recycled content, its environmental benefits remain modest, particularly at low recycled-content percentages (<50%). Overall, these results emphasize that prematurely prioritizing CR may limit the availability of feedstock for long-lived applications and increase reliance on higher-impact materials.

Keywords Flexible mixed polyolefins; Recycling; Sustainability; Circularity

1. Introduction

An annual 13.7 Mt of post-household plastic packaging waste in Europe is categorized as so-called flexibles: film, lidding, bags, and wrappings [1]. Flexibles consist mainly of polyolefins (POs), the polymer family containing polyethylene (PE) and polypropylene (PP), with PE dominating (8.5 Mt), followed by PP (2.5 Mt) [1]. After collection to material recovery facilities (MRFs), these materials are typically sorted into bales such as DSD 310 (Plastic Film), DSD 323-2 (Flexible PO Items), and DSD 352 (Mixed Plastics New, previously labeled as DSD 350) [2]. DSD 310 bales are typically rich in PE and are referred to as “PE Film” bales, while DSD 323-2 bales contain a more significant amount of PP. For example, Lase et al. [3] reported a PE film content of 74% in DSD 310, in comparison with only 35% PE film and a PP film content of 17% in DSD 323-2 (all numbers expressed as % in this manuscript are mass percentages). As such, the latter are often referred to as “MPO Flex” bales [4]. Both DSD 310 and DSD 323 can contain non-PO materials, such as barrier polymers like polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyamide (PA), or ethylene vinyl alcohol (EVOH) [5].

Flexibles are often printed and/or contain adhesives [6], complicating recycling. At the end of the sorting effort in the MRF, the remaining non-sorted (flexible and rigid) plastics are gathered in the DSD 352 bale, called “Mixed Plastics.” This bale has a very diverse composition and—depending on the region and whether or not the region has a deposit system for bottles—can contain a great deal of PET [7]. Nonetheless, studies have shown that even this bale still contains a significant amount of (flexible) POs, ranging from 30% to 60% [8,9]. Aside from these formalized sorting bales, industrial efforts have been made to specifically sort for bales containing only flexible PP, called “PP Film” bales [3], but the implementation of this approach remains the exception rather than the rule.

There is currently a consensus that only the relatively high-purity PE Film (310) bales can and will be recycled back into (flexible) film applications, most of which are garbage bags today. To increase quality, additional pretreatment and/or blending with virgin or post-commercial low-density polyethylene (LDPE) can be introduced [3,10–12]. Significant research was done by the CEFLEX industrial consortium to improve the quality of MPO Flex bales by applying post-sorting, hot washing, improved extrusion, and de-odorization [3,10]. Although this so-called quality recycling process (QRP) results in significantly higher production costs, the trade-off is at least partially justified by the superior quality of the recycled materials and their greater versatility within a circular economy [13]. However, in the current-day economic climate, in which many European recyclers are going out of business [14,15], industrial implementation of this QRP process has yet to materialize.

Hence, there is still a significant amount of flexible MPO (fMPO) material in the European plastic waste system, coming from MPO Flex and Mixed Plastic bales (DSD 323 and 352, respectively) with varying levels of purity. This material currently lacks a closed-loop (i.e., flexible packaging to flexible packaging) destination, and—without legal frameworks being effectively implemented—there is no economic incentive to further pretreat it for higher purity. This study focuses on European fMPO; MPO derived from rigid plastics, despite being equally significant within the plastics system, is excluded due to its different collection and sorting methodologies and its unique challenges, which fall outside the scope of the present research.

Recycling plants using fMPO bales as feedstock typically improve the quality of the as-received bales via a float-sink method that removes the sinking non-POs and some of the multi-layer materials; the material may also be passed through melt filtration at the end of the extruder [16]. This fMPO is then typically recycled into thick-walled (cross-section: >5 mm) products [11,12,17]. A whole array of such products exist (see Table S1 in the Supplementary Information), some of which are quite innovative and technically challenging. Still, by far the most iconic of these thick-walled products is the bench, in which fMPO replaces cast iron, wood, or concrete. Mechanically recycled MPO has demonstrated robust performance and durability, making it a valuable material for outdoor applications [18]. Its resilience against weathering and impact, advantage of relatively lower environmental impacts to produce [19], and suitability for long-term use align well with both the demands of these market segments and the circular economy principles of value retention through durability and recyclability [20,21]. Thus, recycled fMPO is established as a competitive and functional material for such applications, and this industry has steadily grown over the past decades [22]. There is limited information on the market size of these types of products; yet, based on an analysis of PRODCOM data and consultation with industry experts, we estimate a total European market size of around 1 Mt per annum, of which around 50% might be fulfilled with fMPO (more details on this calculation are provided in Section S2.1). Nevertheless, despite its obvious advantages, this recycling path is often referred to as “downcycling,” and its future is debated.

There is growing interest in chemical recycling (CR) via the pyrolysis of fMPO as a potential alternative [8], producing a high-quality feedstock suitable for applications such as food packaging [23]. The high carbon content of fMPO makes it an attractive input feedstock for CR, particularly pyrolysis [24,25]. While mechanical recycling (MR) typically has a lower environmental impact, CR provides an oil that can be cracked back into building blocks such as ethylene and propylene, which can then be used toward the production of virgin-quality polymers [24,26–28], albeit at lower yields [4,29].

As both MR and CR offer distinct advantages and disadvantages, existing research recognizes the importance of working toward non-competitive, complementary cascades between these recycling technologies [19,24,28,30,31]. With waste generation expected to increase [4,32] and growing societal and

political awareness of the importance of an adequate plastics waste-management system [33,34], it is essential to establish optimal recycling routes and material applications.

Regarding fMPO, this raises the important question of whether the current system of MR for thick-walled products should remain a priority destination or whether fMPO should be used in the future as input for pyrolysis instead. This manuscript aims to deliver numbers to feed this discussion based on a systems-level analysis of the role of fMPO in the future circular plastics system along the 2030 timeline in the European Union (EU) 27+3, where “27” refers to the EU member states and “3” refers to the non-EU countries of Norway, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom. Toward this purpose, this paper first presents a refinement of an existing material flow analysis (MFA) that calculates the amounts of fMPO that will be available in Europe in 2030. These amounts are referred to as the “system’s capacity” in this study, meaning the capacity of our waste-management system to provide this feedstock. Based on process yields, estimated market demand, and 2030 recycled-content targets in packaging, it is then investigated whether this amount of fMPO would be sufficient to satisfy the 2030 market demand for both MR for thick-walled products and CR (by pyrolysis) for PE food packaging. For the latter, it is assumed that 10% of the required recycled polymer content in flexible PE packaging [35] will be provided via the CR of fMPO, wherein the recycling rate is calculated via a mass-balance approach.

If both demands cannot be satisfied, some form of prioritization will be required regarding where to send the fMPO. To objectively propose a prioritization approach, this work carries out a sustainability and circularity analysis at the product level. For each target product (i.e., benches or flexible PE packaging), this product-centered perspective evaluates which material is most sustainable to use, comparing fMPO-derived feedstock against alternative materials such as virgin plastics and—in the case of the bench—wood and concrete as well. The goal is to provide a critical evaluation of whether fMPO should be directed toward MR for thick-walled products or CR for packaging applications, and, if so, which allocation pathway offers greater overall sustainability and circularity benefits for the available fMPO volumes. The scope and system boundaries of these research questions are summarized in Fig. 1. In this figure and in the subsequent sections of this study, we consider pyrolysis to be the route followed for CR. Other pathways that produce valuable chemical yields, such as hydrogenolysis or gasification [36], are not considered within the scope of this manuscript.

Fig. 1. Scope and system boundaries of this study. Here, “system’s capacity” refers to the availability of fMPO for mechanical recycling and pyrolysis (depicted as chemical recycling). Sustainability and circularity are based on a product assessment of fMPO products. Plastics recycling and metal recycling are accounted for in the life-cycle assessment as avoided burdens only.

This study is particularly relevant for its focus on the material, environmental, and circularity impacts of a potential shift in feedstock allocation between CR and MR. Such a shift introduces trade-offs between competing end-uses, each characterized by different lifespans, environmental footprints, and societal roles. The

MR route supports the production of durable and long-lived product applications at the expense of closed-loop recycling, whereas the CR route toward packaging helps preserve food and reduces food waste but might result in faster turnover and increased resource consumption.

2. Methods

2.1 Material flow analysis

To examine the prospective role of fMPO in the circular economy, it is essential to first understand the feedstock availability and market demand. An MFA is used to assess the market availability of waste fMPO for either MR or CR, which is then set against the expected demands. Demand for MR is based on a projection from the Eurostat PRODCOM market demand [22], validated by expert opinion. Demand for CR is based on the projected demand for flexible food contact packaging and the 10% recycled content requirement (by 2030) in contact-sensitive packaging dictated by the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR) [35]. Given the stringency of food-contact regulations, it is assumed that this 10% recycled content comes exclusively from the CR route, which is fed by fMPO. Details of the market demand assumptions are provided in Section S2.1 in the Supplementary Information.

2.1.1 Feedstock-availability assumptions

The MFA by Lase et al. [4] is used as a basis for the MFA in this study, as it provides an overview for five sectors and 10 polymers, including six scenarios focusing on the EU 27+3 for 2030. The availability of fMPO from the MPO Flex and Mixed Plastics bales has been extrapolated from that work. It should be noted that the Mixed Plastics bales may also contain some rigid PO (HDPE and PP rigid), the mass flows of which are excluded from the current study. In addition, no additional empirical composition research was conducted within the present study, as Lase et al. [4] already extensively aggregated data on waste input compositions from a compilation of reports and the literature [3,24,37–42]. The MFA in the current study includes the outputs of both sorting and reprocessing, where the latter includes shredding, washing, and drying prior to the actual recycling step of either MR (thick-walled mechanical recycling) or CR (pyrolysis). Residual treatment is applied for all rejects and losses. This study only considers pyrolysis as an alternative to the MR of fMPO; other CR technologies, as well as solvent-based recycling, are excluded. The mass flows are modeled using the e!Sankey 5 pro software [43].

2.1.2 Scenarios

Scenarios with various priorities for MR and CR as destinations for fMPO recycling are developed, denoted as S1, S2, and S3. Table 1 provides an overview of these scenarios and their respective demand assumptions, with the associated calculations provided in Section S2.1 of the Supplementary Information. In S1, full priority is given to the market demand for thick-walled MR. In S2, full priority is given to the market demand for CR by pyrolysis, assuming that the mass-balance calculations are proportional—that is, only the produced polymers can claim recycled content credits (and not base chemicals or fuels). Finally, in S3, full priority is again given to market demand for CR by pyrolysis, but here the assumption is that the more beneficial fuel-exempt mass balancing is used for CR, as recently described in the EU Commission’s draft proposal [44]. In a fuel-exempt mass-balancing scenario, the proportional amounts of both base chemicals and polymers receive recycled content credits, which can then be attributed entirely to the polymer produced by the cracker. Hence, less CR input is required to achieve the same target. Finally, for all future scenarios (S1–S3), the required tonnages of fMPO are calculated backward from the market demand, using the yield transfer coefficients reported by Lase et al. [4].

Table 1 Overview of the chosen scenarios, their supporting argumentation, description, and assumptions for input and output quantities (assumptions based on calculations provided in Section S2.1 in the Supplementary Information).

Scenario and description	Assumed output demand (annual)	Yields of priority recycling route	Required fMPO input to
--------------------------	--------------------------------	------------------------------------	------------------------

			achieve output demand (annual)
S1: MR priority <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fMPO sent to thick-walled MR until demand is satisfied • Overflow (if any) sent to CR • Credits calculated as polymer-only mass balancing 	MR recyclate required for thick-walled products: 580 kt	95% polymer	611 kt
S2: CR priority, polymer-only <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fMPO sent to CR until demand is satisfied. • CR credits calculated as polymer-only mass balancing • Overflow (if any) sent to thick-walled MR 	CR recyclate for PE flexible packaging (10% recycled content): 360 kt	22% polymer 57% chemicals (not counted as recycled content)	1652 kt
S3: CR priority, fuel-exempt <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fMPO sent to CR until demand is satisfied • CR credits calculated as fuel-exempt mass balancing • Overflow (if any) sent to thick-walled MR 	CR recyclate for PE flexible packaging (10% recycled content): 360 kt	22% polymer 57% chemicals (counted as recycled content)	456 kt

2.1.3 Out-of-scope: MR of PE Film (310) bales to non-food packaging films

As mentioned previously, this work only considers the recycling destinations of the more challenging fMPO, as it is assumed that relatively pure PE Film (310) bales will be sent to MR recycling and then back into film applications. With the current state of the art in MR, this fraction could be relatively high quality from a technical point of view [10] but would not be suitable for food contact (this research assumes PE for food contact is provided via the CR route instead). As such, the MR of PE Film should provide enough materials to meet the recycled content target for non-contact-sensitive packaging, which is 35% by 2030 [35]. Detailed calculations for the feedstock availability for non-food-packaging films are provided in Section S2.2.

2.2 Sustainability and circularity assessments

This section evaluates the sustainability and circularity implications of the two recycling pathways for the end-use of fMPO: (1) MR into thick-walled products, using a park bench as a representative product; and (2) CR via pyrolysis into food-grade flexible packaging. The analysis is performed from a product perspective, beginning with a demand for specific products (1 park bench used for 30 years and 1 kg of food-grade LDPE packaging) and evaluating how recycled fMPO performs environmentally and in terms of circularity when used to produce them. The results are benchmarked against conventional material options (wood, cast iron, and virgin HDPE for benches; virgin LDPE for packaging) to assess whether recycled fMPO is indeed a valuable substitute.

This approach makes it possible to compare the recycled products from each pathway in terms of how well they meet real-world needs and replace conventional materials. By doing so, this study aims to offer a targeted understanding of how the treatment and use of fMPO can contribute to more sustainable and circular material systems.

2.2.1 Life-cycle assessment

Environmental performance was evaluated through a life-cycle assessment (LCA) following the ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 standards, which specify four phases: goal and scope definition, life-cycle inventory analysis, life-cycle impact assessment, and life-cycle interpretation [45].

2.2.1.1 Goal and scope definition

The goal of the LCA study was to determine which fMPO conversion pathway delivers better sustainability and circularity outcomes: MR into thick-walled products or CR into food-grade packaging. The assessment

was performed per functional unit of product, defined according to service delivery—for thick-walled products, one bench providing 30 years of outdoor seating functionality; for packaging, the provision of 1 kg of LDPE packaging with varying levels of (CR) recycled content (0%, 10%, 50%, and 100%). A more detailed description of the LCA methods is provided in Section S3.1 in the Supplementary Information, including details on the energy consumption costs of both pathways.

2.2.2 Circularity assessment

To evaluate product circularity, the widely used Product Circularity Indicator (PCI) developed by Bracquené et al. [46] was applied. The PCI quantifies how effectively a product retains its material value by combining three key product characteristics: (1) the mass of virgin and recycled materials and their respective process efficiencies; (2) the mass of unrecoverable waste (and, consequently, the mass of recovered or circular materials); and (3) a utility factor that accounts for the length and intensity of the product's use. The PCI score ranges from 0 to 1.0, where 1 represents a circular product with full material recirculation, and 0 corresponds to a completely linear product. The PCI is calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{PCI} = (1 - \text{LFI}) \cdot X \quad (1)$$

where LFI is the linear flow index, representing the proportion of non-circular flows, and X is the utility factor, accounting for product durability and intensity of use. The LFI and X are calculated as follows:

$$\text{LFI} = \frac{V+W+\frac{1}{2}(|R|+|C|)}{V_{\text{linear}}+W_{\text{linear}}} \quad (2)$$

$$X = \left(\frac{L}{L_d}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{U}{U_d}\right) \quad (3)$$

where V is the virgin material input, W is the total unrecoverable waste (including production losses and end-of-life waste), R is the net exchange of recycled materials between systems (in – out), C is the net exchange of reused components (in – out), and V_{linear} and W_{linear} are the total virgin input and waste output in a linear scenario. All mass flows (V , W , R , C , V_{linear} , and W_{linear}) are expressed in units of mass per product over its total lifetime. The term $\frac{1}{2} \times (|R| + |C|)$ accounts for flows that are only partially circular, as their fate depends on other product systems. L is the actual product lifetime, L_d is the design lifetime (as intended by the manufacturer), U is the actual use intensity (e.g., uses per year), and U_d is the average or expected use intensity.

The PCI was applied to all products except the wooden bench, for which the circularity score was adapted using principles from the Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) [47], to account for the renewable, biogenic nature of sustainably sourced timber.

2.2.3 Sustainability–circularity integration

To integrate the sustainability and circularity assessments, a Sustainability–Circularity Index (SCI) is proposed. The SCI reflects the amount of circularity benefit achieved per euro of environmental price, where the environmental price represents the normalized environmental burden based on the Environmental Pricing (EP) method, which converts midpoint impact categories into monetary equivalents [48]. By combining these parameters, the SCI provides a hybrid metric to evaluate trade-offs between environmental impacts and circularity performance. It is calculated as the ratio of the product's circularity score to its associated environmental cost, as follows:

$$\text{SCI} = \frac{\text{PCI}}{\text{Environmental price (€)}} \quad (4)$$

In this formula, a higher SCI value indicates better sustainability–circularity performance, as it represents the achievement of greater circularity for a lower environmental cost. The objective is for the circularity to be as high as possible and the environmental price to be as low as possible, thereby maximizing the SCI.

To ensure a balanced, product-level comparison between MR and CR routes, the analysis was standardized using an equal reference mass of material for the packaging applications (83 kg), corresponding to the amount

of plastic used in a single bench. This approach enabled a fair comparison of the SCI across different fMPO product applications. The resulting SCI values reflect how effectively a given mass of recycled material contributes to the circularity per euro of environmental cost across functionally distinct outputs. Products made from alternative materials (e.g., wood, cast iron, and virgin LDPE) were also included as benchmarks to provide a multi-material perspective on the comparison.

It should be noted that this index is a preliminary proposal for bridging sustainability and circularity assessments. In future applications, alternative formulations and improvements could be explored. However, for this study, the PCI/€ structure was selected to maintain consistency with the broader interpretation that higher index values indicate more favorable outcomes.

2.3 Assumptions and limitations

The first limitation is that, in the material availability reported by Lase et al. [4], who included a sensitivity analysis of their own, the scenarios do not account for a decrease in fMPO waste (e.g., because of a design for recycling future) or an increase in fMPO waste (e.g., because of an increase in waste collection). Another limitation involves the different CR yields used for the MFA and sustainability and circularity calculations. The CR recycling yield (i.e., 79% under fuel-exempt mass balancing; Table 1) used in the MFA scenarios is based on the work of Lase et al. [4] to ensure consistency throughout the MFAs, as that work was used as the basis for this paper's MFA study. However, for the subsequent sustainability and circularity assessments, the focus of this paper was not to conduct LCA calculations of our own—which would be a repeat of the existing literature—but rather to compare the MR and CR destinations using the new SCI indicator. As such, environmental impact data was used from existing and well-cited studies. For the CR pathway by pyrolysis, this data came from Jeswani et al. [26]. However, their calculated yields for CR are relatively modest, at 62% (see Table S5 in the Supplementary Information). In both cases, the authors made the methodological choice to maintain consistency within the separate calculations; therefore, Lase et al.'s [4] CR yield of 79% was used for the MFA and Jeswani et al.'s [26] CR yield of 62% was used within the environmental calculations. The manuscript addresses these shortcomings by including an MFA sensitivity analysis that varies both the feedstock availability (+/- 25%) and the mass-balanced pyrolysis efficiency (50%–90%), provided in Section S2.3 in the Supplementary Information. A conscious choice was made to retain the more conservative 62% CR yield of Jeswani et al. in the environmental calculations, as the source manuscript had already compiled this number from consultancy, the literature, and industrial data. Furthermore, this number aligns well with the reported value in another recent study [31]. While a higher yield number would of course improve the SCI scores for CR, this study aimed to present data as reliably as possible, rather than optimizing the outcome for any of the routes. For the same reason, conservative end-of-life options were chosen for the MR route, as these are more in line with current practices than an optimized recycling route.

The end-of-life scenarios used in the environmental sustainability and circularity assessments rely on simplified assumptions: All fMPO benches are assumed to be incinerated, while virgin HDPE benches are assumed to be recycled, despite the potential for alternative pathways that have not yet been explored. This conservative assumption slightly disadvantages the MR route, but it was applied because the recyclability and material properties of virgin HDPE are well established, whereas the long-term performance of recycling an already mechanically recycled fMPO bench is not yet well documented. Likewise, potential second-life or multi-cycle recycling scenarios were not considered. In principle, both the thick-walled MR products and the virgin-grade packaging derived from CR could re-enter MR or CR routes at the end of their respective service lives. However, these loops would occur on different timescales and would require further assumptions about quality retention and system boundaries.

The viability of pyrolysis for producing food-grade recyclate is also taken as a given, excluding contamination constraints at pyrolysis and cracker input. This reliance on secondary data limits the ability to adapt the calculation parameters and run sensitivity analyses to reflect evolving technological realities and modeling choices. Additionally, an equivalent energy mix was used across both the LCA and MCI calculations based on projections by Jeswani et al. [26] for the year 2030 to ensure comparability; however, possible future variations in energy systems are acknowledged but not modeled due to data constraints.

From a material availability perspective, it should also be stressed that the potential substitutability of materials by biobased alternatives was not included in the demand calculations, as it has been assumed that substitution by such products would not have significantly changed by 2030 [49]. Thus, potential substitutes for thick-walled mechanically recycled products (e.g., wood) and for food packaging films (e.g., biobased film) were not taken into account in the MFA calculations.

From a product perspective, the material substitution ratio of fMPO to HDPE in benches was estimated based on functional performance ranges reported in the literature. While this provides a reasonable basis for comparison, it remains an approximation that is subject to uncertainty. To address this issue, a sensitivity analysis was conducted to capture the potential impact of varying substitution ratios. Similarly, the assumed product lifetimes for benches were informed by expert opinion and standard practices but may differ significantly in real-world settings due to site-specific factors such as climate, intensity of use, and maintenance. This variability was likewise explored through a sensitivity analysis to assess its influence on the results. Both sensitivity analyses are briefly discussed in the results section and are detailed in Section S4 in the Supplementary Information.

While this study adopts a product perspective, both MR and CR remain valid technologies for waste management in their own right. To acknowledge this dimension, an LCA comparing the two pathways based on the treatment of 1 tonne of fMPO waste is provided in Section S3.5. These results reflect a waste-oriented perspective and are included to inform broader discussions on the environmental implications of managing fMPO waste, regardless of its end-use product.

Finally, it should be noted that CR technologies are still evolving. Advances in process efficiency, scalability, and energy intensity reduction may improve the future sustainability and circularity performance of CR systems [50,51].

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Material flow analysis

The following figures show the MFA for all scenarios. The waste destinations of thick-walled MR, CR (by pyrolysis), and residual treatment are respectively shown in purple, blue, and salmon-colored boxes. The material flows for LDPE (in orange) and PP film (in blue) are included. However, as there is comparatively little PP film in the material flow chart, those lines are close to invisible; the text below each flow describes the mass of PP film.

Fig. 2 shows the MFA for S1, in which thick-walled MR is prioritized over CR as a waste management destination. The figure shows that there is more than sufficient fMPO available to meet this demand. Thus, the remainder of the fMPO could still be sent to CR, which is credited here using polymer-only mass balancing (resulting in a 22% polymer yield of the CR process). However, the remaining fMPO would be insufficient to cover the CR output demand of 360 kt.

S1

Fig. 2. MFA for S1, a 2030 scenario in which thick-walled MR is prioritized as the destination for fMPO waste streams, based on demand for thick-walled MR products. Comparatively little PP Flex is present in the material flow chart, making its lines close to invisible; however, the text below each flow describes the mass of PP Flex.

In S2, CR is prioritized over thick-walled MR, and the mass-balancing of CR remains based on polymer-only mass balancing. Fig. 3 shows that, to obtain the required 360 kt output, an input of 1652 kt is required, which cannot be provided entirely by the available fMPO streams. Therefore, 934 kt would still be required from other sources to satisfy the demand for CR.

S2

Fig. 3. MFA for S2, a 2030 scenario in which CR (pyrolysis) is prioritized as the destination for fMPO waste streams, based on the demand of CR for a waste-to-polymer mass-balance approach. Comparatively little PP Flex is present in the material flow chart, making the lines close to invisible, but the text below each flow describes the mass of PP Flex.

In the last scenario, S3, CR still has priority; however, the (credited) efficiency of the process is significantly higher due to the inclusion of the amount of base chemicals in the recycled polymer credits (based on fuel-exempt mass-balancing calculations, which result in a counted 79% polymer yield from the CR process according to Lase et al. [4]). As a result, only 456 kt of fMPO is needed to satisfy the demand for recycled content via CR. Fig. 4 shows that, with this higher efficiency, there is sufficient material available to cover the

demand for CR, and an excess of 262 kt of fMPO can even be used for thick-walled MR. This excess amount, however, is insufficient to fully meet the demand for thick-walled products.

S3

Fig. 4. MFA for S3, a 2030 scenario in which CR (pyrolysis) is prioritized as the destination for fMPO waste streams, based on the CR demand for a waste-to-polymer + base chemical mass-balance approach (fuel-exempt mass-balancing approach). Comparatively little PP Flex is present in the material flow chart, making its lines close to invisible, but the text below each flow describes the mass of PP Flex.

The results show that, in all three scenarios, there is not enough fMPO to satisfy both the demand for CR and the demand for thick-walled MR. Additionally, the sensitivity analysis (Section S2.3 in the Supplementary Information) shows that changing the feedstock availability (+/- 25%) and the mass-balanced pyrolysis efficiency (50%–90%) still results in insufficient materials being available to meet both the demands of CR and those of MR. Thus, even under the most favorable conditions, it is still necessary to make decisions on the future management of fMPO waste.

While not central to the presented work, it is relevant to include the feedstock availability for non-food-contact flexible films in this discussion. Based on the detailed calculations included in Section S2.2, this annual demand is 3130 kt in 2030, whereas the business-as-usual MR of PE film would only provide 2050 kt (calculated from Ref. [4]). Thus, it is concerning that the future demand for recycled content in non-food-contact flexible films would likewise not be met by the MR of PE film, even if the feedstock availability increased by 25% (resulting in 2560 kt per annum). Based on technical material property requirements, without additional waste pretreatment, this deficit simply cannot come from the MR of fMPO, and the outputs of CR are already “spoken for” by the demand for food-contact packaging. Even in a potential fourth scenario, S4 (worked out in Table S4), in which all available fMPO goes to CR under a fuel-exempt mass balance, the surplus after meeting the demand for food-contact flexible packaging would be limited to 206 kt per annum, which is still insufficient to close the gap.

Overall, these findings imply a systemic failure to reach the recycled content targets for flexible packaging when the feedstock for this demand is restricted to waste from flexible plastic packaging only. This feedstock conflict is partially policy-driven, as policy frameworks create flat demands across the sector (e.g., the 10% recycled content required for contact-sensitive packaging by 2030 in PPWR [35]), without necessarily considering the implications across the plastics waste-management system.

3.2 Environmental sustainability and circularity assessments

This section presents the environmental and circularity performance of the products made from mechanically and chemically recycled fMPO. Using LCAs and the PCI, this analysis compares fMPO-derived products (i.e., a park bench and food-grade flexible packaging) with conventional alternatives. To integrate the environmental and circularity performance into a single metric, the SCI is introduced.

Across most midpoint impact categories, the recycled fMPO bench outperforms its material counterparts in 16 out of 18 categories. In Climate Change (GWP100), the wooden bench outperforms all other materials (14 kg CO₂-eq. per functional unit) with biogenic carbon storage not taken into account, whereas the virgin HDPE bench leads in Freshwater Ecotoxicity Potential (FETP) (4.1E-01 kg 1,4-DB-eq.). The cast iron bench shows the highest impacts overall, notably in Terrestrial Ecotoxicity (32 000 kg 1,4-DB-eq.) and Metal Depletion (170 kg Cu-eq.). The results for all impact categories and products are provided in Table S12 in the Supplementary Information.

Normalization through environmental pricing shows that the total environmental cost of the MR fMPO bench (24.02 EUR) is only slightly higher than that of the wooden bench (21.40 EUR) and is lower than those of the virgin HDPE (36.07 EUR) and cast iron (582.75 EUR) benches. These results suggest that MR fMPO is a viable and environmentally competitive feedstock for durable, thick-walled applications, at a similar level to wood.

In terms of packaging, the results for varying percentages of CR content in food-grade LDPE show that the environmental performance is best when high proportions of CR material are used. The total environmental cost decreases from 0.359 EUR for 0% CR content to 0.239 EUR for 100% CR, with the latter outperforming all mixed-content scenarios across nearly all midpoint categories. These findings highlight the risk of diminishing returns when only small fractions of CR material are incorporated, emphasizing the importance of maximizing recycled content to achieve meaningful environmental gains. The environmental impacts are provided in Table S13.

3.2.1 Product circularity indicator results

As displayed in Fig. 5, among the bench materials, cast iron achieves the highest PCI (0.82), reflecting its durability and high recyclability, followed by MR fMPO (0.74) and FSC-certified wood (0.68). Virgin HDPE benches have the lowest PCI in this product category (0.18). In contrast, packaging products show much lower PCI values. Even with 100% chemically recycled LDPE content, the packaging product PCI only reaches 0.26. As the recycled content decreases, the PCI declines to 0.15 and 0.08 for blends with 50% and 10% recycled content, respectively. Virgin LDPE packaging achieves the lowest circularity score (0.06).

These results reinforce the idea proposed by others [52–54] that product lifespan and material recovery are critical drivers of circularity. While the circularity of flexible packaging is improved by higher recycled content, this product's short use-phase fundamentally limits its absolute circularity in comparison with more durable products. This limitation is inherent to the packaging application itself and would equally constrain PCI scores if the same product were made from mechanically recycled or virgin material. This is reflected in the utility factor of the PCI, which accounts for product lifespan and frequency of use. However, in applications such as food packaging, increased durability may not be a viable design solution due to specific functional and hygienic requirements. In such cases, it is acknowledged that the PCI results are best interpreted in relation to other products with similar use profiles [55,56].

Fig. 5. Product Circularity Indicator scores of two product categories (benches and packaging) and their material counterparts.

3.2.2 Circularity per unit of environmental price paid

To integrate circularity performance with environmental impact, a new ratio is introduced: the SCI, which expresses a product's circularity score (PCI) relative to its environmental cost, as described in Eq. 4. This indicator captures the amount of circular value delivered per unit of environmental burden, expressed in environmental costs, enabling a more integrated comparison between product alternatives.

As mentioned earlier, to ensure a balanced comparison across functionally distinct products, the analysis was standardized using an equal reference mass of material (83 kg) for a fair evaluation of the SCI across different applications. Products made from alternative materials (e.g., wood, cast iron, and virgin LDPE) were included as benchmarks for a multi-material perspective on the trade-offs between circularity and environmental performance.

Among benches (Fig. 6, left side), MR fMPO and FSC-certified wood achieve the highest PCI/€ ratios ($\sim 0.031 \text{ EUR}^{-1}$), indicating that their circularity potential relative to their environmental impacts is the highest of the group. Virgin HDPE benches score much lower ($\sim 0.005 \text{ EUR}^{-1}$), while cast iron—despite having the highest PCI—ranks lowest due to the environmental impacts associated with the high energy consumption required to cast the parts.

For packaging (Fig. 6, right side), the PCI/€ ratio strongly correlates with its recycled content. Packaging made with 100% chemically recycled LDPE achieves the highest efficiency (0.013 EUR^{-1}), while the ratio declines to 0.006 EUR^{-1} and 0.0027 EUR^{-1} for packaging with 50% and 10% recycled content, respectively. Virgin LDPE packaging achieves the lowest PCI/€ (0.002 EUR^{-1}). The overall low results when compared with MR for benches suggest that, despite the potential circularity and environmental gains CR might bring to the packaging industry, the short use-phase remains its biggest constraint.

Fig. 6. SCI scores for benches and food-grade packaging; higher scores are preferred.

It is important to note that, while SCI has been calculated using a standardized input mass to enable cross-functional comparison, the underlying products serve fundamentally different purposes. In this formulation, the SCI is best interpreted as a way to compare how efficiently a given amount of recycled material delivers circular benefits for each euro of environmental cost, rather than as evidence of the absolute superiority of one product type over another. For example, given 83 kg of recycled feedstock, a long-lived product such as a bench yields more circular value per environmental euro than short-lived packaging, because the PCI captures the benefit of extended service life. Thus, the SCI provides a meaningful and relatively balanced way to explore how different product systems valorize recycled material, without implying a universal ranking between unrelated products. Future methodological developments could address this limitation by refining normalization strategies that better account for differences in product utility.

Given the inherent variability in the technical and processing properties of fMPO [16,57,58], it is essential to evaluate how assumptions about material substitutability and product use time influence fMPO's overall environmental performance. Therefore, two key sources of uncertainty were addressed in a sensitivity analysis: (1) the substitutability of fMPO for virgin HDPE from a waste perspective, and (2) the effective lifetime of a bench from a product perspective. These results are added in Section S4 in the Supplementary Information.

4. Conclusion and outlook

This study set out to investigate prospective fMPO recycling pathways in the 2030 circular plastics economy. From a feedstock-availability perspective, insufficient fMPO waste is available to satisfy both the demand for CR (by pyrolysis) and that for thick-walled MR in 2030, even if both waste collection (+25%) and mass-balanced pyrolysis efficiencies (up to 90%) significantly improve. Thus, a technology-agnostic method was proposed to compare sustainability and circularity between recycling destinations for fMPO: MR for thick-walled products (e.g., a bench) or CR for virgin-like feedstock for contact-sensitive packaging.

The results show that—exclusively from a sustainability and circularity point of view and with projected 2030 infrastructure, recycling efficiencies, and product lifetimes—directing fMPO to thick-walled MR is preferable. Utilizing fMPO for CR to produce virgin-grade packaging yields only modest gains, particularly when recycled content levels are low (10%–50%) and because product lifetimes are short, as is typical for packaging.

The newly developed SCI ratio shows that MR benches and FSC-certified wood products achieve the highest circularity-to-environmental-cost ratios among the studied products, while flexible packaging—even with high CR content—remains constrained by its inherently short use-phase. It is important to note that, in this study, packaging results are based only on food-contact LDPE film and do not include other potential

packaging types, functional requirements, or lifetime differences. In this sense, the low PCI values observed for packaging largely reflect the short-lived nature of this application and the proportion of virgin to recycled material used, rather than strictly stemming from the technology involved. It should also be noted that the SCI indicator used in this study is a preliminary proposal for bridging sustainability and circularity assessments. Future applications should explore alternative formulations and improvements.

While CR technologies will continue to evolve under current policy frameworks and will play a role in increasing packaging circularity, our results highlight the importance of evaluating recycling technologies together with—rather than in isolation from—their potential applications. We argue that, from both a circularity and sustainability perspective, the performance of a technology cannot be meaningfully assessed without considering the product system in which its outputs are used. In other words, the environmental and circularity benefits of a recycling route are inseparable from the lifespan and function of the products it ultimately creates. Recycled materials applied in short-lived, fast-cycle products will inherently show lower material and value retention than the same material applied in long-lived products. As such, prematurely prioritizing pyrolysis as the main valorization route for fMPO primarily to supply flexible packaging may bring a cost to broader sustainability and circularity goals, while also creating feedstock scarcity for industries manufacturing durable goods—potentially forcing a shift toward alternative materials with higher environmental impacts.

Due to collection and process losses, fMPO leaks out of the material system, regardless of which of the investigated recycling route(s) or combination thereof is chosen. As such, it will be challenging to meet 2030 recycled content targets for all types of flexible packaging. Nonetheless, the future availability of waste fMPO is subject to both positive and negative influences. The fMPO stream is never a target stream for sorting; it is a result of striking a balance between cost and purity for waste that includes both PP and PE, which is primarily packaging. Improved collection rates in countries that are not yet oriented toward high-purity sorting would increase the overall European volume of available fMPO plastic waste, even as more advanced sorting processes in other countries would locally decrease fMPO volumes. Additionally, this study assumed that all reject streams from pretreatment go to residual treatment, but such materials might still hold potential for either MR or CR, such as via the gasification route [29]. Significant research is currently being done with regard to valorizing the DKR 350, for example [8,59]. Finally, the evolution of waste exports and recycled polymer imports will have a significant impact on future pathways. Similarly, there is a significant call from the European recycling industry to regulate the imports of cheap and often untraceable recycled plastics [60]. Whether or not this will result in sufficient available fMPO in the system to satisfy the demands for both MR and CR remains unclear. Until then, prioritization will be required.

A further evaluation, additional to the current work, would be to include calculations in which environmental footprints are converted into economic costs, in order to form a comprehensive one-in-all comparison between the recycling routes of a single waste stream.

Acknowledging that both food-grade packaging and thick-walled applications represent important and growing market segments, this analysis highlights the need for strategic material allocation. While both MR and CR have roles to play within a circular economy, the findings of this study emphasize that the narrative that using fMPO for bench-like products would be “downcycling” is flawed.

Abbreviations

CR	Chemical recycling
EOFP	Ecosystem damage ozone formation potential (kg NO _x -eq)
EoL	End of life
EP	Environmental pricing
EVOH	Ethylene vinyl alcohol
FEP	Freshwater eutrophication potential (kg P-eq. to freshwater)

FETP	Freshwater ecotoxicity potential (kg 1,4-DB-eq)
FFP	Fossil-fuel resource scarcity potential (kg oil-eq)
fMPO	Flexible mixed polyolefins
FU	Functional unit
GWP100	Global warming potential over 100 years (kg CO ₂ -eq)
HDPE	High-density polyethylene
HOFp	Human damage ozone formation potential (kg NO _x -eq)
HTPc	Human carcinogenic toxicity potential (1,4-DCB eq. emitted to urban air)
HTPnc	Human noncarcinogenic toxicity potential (1,4-DCB eq. emitted to urban air)
HVR	Heavy vacuum residue
IRP	Ionizing radiation potential (kBq Co-60 to air eq.)
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LCA	Life-cycle assessment
LCI	Life-cycle inventory
LCIA	Life-cycle impact assessment
LDPE	Low-density polyethylene
LLDPE	Linear low-density polyethylene
LOP	Land occupation potential (m ² ·a)
MEP	Marine eutrophication potential (kg N-eq. to marine water)
METP	Marine ecotoxicity potential (1,4-DCB eq. emitted to seawater)
MFA	Material flow analysis
MPO	Mixed polyolefins
MR	Mechanical recycling
MRF	Material recovery facility
ODP	Stratospheric ozone depletion potential (kg CFC11-eq.)
PA	Polyamide
PCI	Product Circularity Indicator
PE	Polyethylene
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
PMFP	Particulate matter formation potential (kg PM _{2.5} -eq.)
PP	Polypropylene
PPWR	Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation
QRP	Quality recycling process
SCI	Sustainability–Circularity Index
SOP	Mineral resource scarcity potential (kg Cu-eq.)
TAP	Terrestrial acidification potential (kg SO ₂ -eq.)

TETP	Terrestrial ecotoxicity potential (1,4-DCB eq. emitted to industrial soil)
VM	Virgin materials
WCP	Water consumption potential (m ³)

Declaration of competing interest

The authors have no competing interests to declare.

Acknowledgements

This research was partially funded by the Horizon Europe project Syschemiq (Grant No. 101059909) for Merel Molenbuur, Steven De Meester, and Kim Ragaert; by the bilateral project Sustainability Assessment with Hahn (DE); and by in-house funding from the CCE department at Maastricht University. The authors would like to thank Diana Cecilia Ruiz Flores, Arnab Chaudhuri, and David Palacios Garcia for the useful discussions, which helped strengthen the research, and Prof. Adisa Azapagic for sharing details on the work done in Jeswani, 2021.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Merel Molenbuur: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing—original draft, Writing—review & editing, Visualization. Cris Garcia-Saravia Ortiz-de-Montellano: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing—original draft, Writing—review & editing, Visualization. Steven De Meester: Writing—review & editing, Yvonne van der Meer: Writing—review & editing, Milad Golkaram: Conceptualization, Methodology, Kim Ragaert: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing—review & editing, Supervision.

References

- [1] Plastics Recyclers Europe, Independent Commodity Intelligence Services. 2023 Flexible films market in Europe. Report. Brussels: Plastics Recyclers Europe; 2023.
- [2] Der Grüne Punkt. Downloads—specifications [Internet]. Cologne: Der Grüne Punkt Holding GmbH & Co. KG; [cited 2024 Oct 18]. Available from: <https://www.gruener-punkt.de/en/downloads>.
- [3] Lase IS, Bashirgonbadi A, van Rhijn F, Dewulf J, Ragaert K, Delva L, et al. Material flow analysis and recycling performance of an improved mechanical recycling process for post-consumer flexible plastics. *Waste Manag* 2022;153:249–63. doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2022.09.002. PMID:36126399
- [4] Lase IS, Tonini D, Caro D, Albizzati PF, Cristóbal J, Roosen M, et al. How much can chemical recycling contribute to plastic waste recycling in Europe? An assessment using material flow analysis modeling. *Resour Conserv Recycling* 2023;192:106916. doi:10.1016/j.resconrec.2023.106916.
- [5] Freitag N, Schneider J, Decottignies V, Fell T, Kucukpinar E, Schlummer M. Waste study on flexible food and non-food packaging: detailed analysis of the plastic composition of european polyethylene-containing waste streams. *Materials* 2024;17(13):3202. doi:10.3390/ma17133202. PMID:38998285
- [6] Lisiecki M, Belé TGA, Ügdüler S, Fiorio R, Astrup TF, De Meester S, et al. Mechanical recycling of printed flexible plastic packaging: the role of binders and pigments. *J Hazard Mater* 2024;472:134375. doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2024.134375. PMID:38691991
- [7] Ragaert K, Huysveld S, Vyncke G, Hubo S, Veelaert L, Dewulf J, et al. Design from recycling: a complex mixed plastic waste case study. *Resour Conserv Recycling* 2020;155:104646. doi:10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.104646.
- [8] Genuino HC, Ruiz MP, Heeres HJ, Kersten SRA. Pyrolysis of mixed plastic waste (DKR-350): effect of washing pre-treatment and fate of chlorine. *Fuel Process Technol* 2022;233:107304. doi:10.1016/j.fuproc.2022.107304.
- [9] Brouwer MT, Thoden van Velzen EU, Augustinus A, Soethoudt H, De Meester S, Ragaert K. Predictive model for the Dutch post-consumer plastic packaging recycling system and implications for the circular economy. *Waste Manag* 2018;71:62–85. doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2017.10.034. PMID:29107509
- [10] Bashirgonbadi A, Saputra Lase I, Delva L, Van Geem KM, De Meester S, Ragaert K. Quality evaluation and economic assessment of an improved mechanical recycling process for post-consumer flexible plastics. *Waste Manag* 2022;153:41–51. doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2022.08.018. PMID:36049271

- [11] Faraca G, Astrup T. Plastic waste from recycling centres: characterisation and evaluation of plastic recyclability. *Waste Manag* 2019;95:388–98. doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2019.06.038. PMID:31351625
- [12] Horodytska O, Valdés FJ, Fullana A. Plastic flexible films waste management—a state of art review. *Waste Manag* 2018;77:413–25. doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2018.04.023. PMID:29691112
- [13] Van Camp N, Lase IS, De Meester S, Hoozée S, Ragaert K. Exposing the pitfalls of plastics mechanical recycling through cost calculation. *Waste Manag* 2024;189:300–13. doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2024.08.017. PMID:39226844
- [14] Santos B. Dutch recycler Stiphout Plastics files for bankruptcy [Internet]. Detroit: Plastics News; 2025 Jan 3 [cited 2025 Mar 21]. Available from: <https://www.sustainableplastics.com/news/dutch-recycler-stiphout-plastics-files-bankruptcy>.
- [15] Scott A. Global plastics glut hurts Europe’s recyclers. *C&EN* 2024;102(4):12.
- [16] Ragaert K, Delva L, Van Geem K. Mechanical and chemical recycling of solid plastic waste. *Waste Manag* 2017;69:24–58. doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2017.07.044. PMID:28823699
- [17] Taqwatomo G, Novriadi D, Marsaputra Panjaitan B, Prasetyo H, Subagyo Y, Eka Mulyono A, et al. Mechanical properties of recycling mixed waste plastic predicted on pallet application using finite element analysis. *E3S Web Conf* 2024;483:03019. doi:10.1051/e3sconf/202448303019.
- [18] Bolong N, Saad I, Asman NSA, Choong WH, Roslan Z. Feasibility of recycled HDPE planks for sustainable furniture applications: a physio-mechanical study. *MATEC Web Conf* 2024;397:03005. doi:10.1051/matecconf/202439703005.
- [19] Garcia-Gutierrez P, Amadei AM, Klenert D, Nessi S, Tonini D, Tosches D, et al. Environmental and economic assessment of plastic waste recycling. Report. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union; 2023.
- [20] Diaz A, Schöggel JP, Reyes T, Baumgartner RJ. Sustainable product development in a circular economy: implications for products, actors, decision-making support and lifecycle information management. *Sustain Prod Consum* 2021;26:1031–45. doi:10.1016/j.spc.2020.12.044.
- [21] den Hollander MC, Bakker CA, Hultink EJ. Product design in a circular economy: development of a typology of key concepts and terms. *J Ind Ecol* 2017;21(3):517–25. doi:10.1111/jiec.12610.
- [22] Prodcom—statistics by product [Internet]. Luxembourg: European Commission, Eurostat; [cited 2025 Jul 8]. Available from: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/prodcom/database>.
- [23] Kusenberg M, Eschenbacher A, Delva L, De Meester S, Delikonstantis E, Stefanidis GD, et al. Towards high-quality petrochemical feedstocks from mixed plastic packaging waste via advanced recycling: the past, present and future. *Fuel Process Technol* 2022;238:107474. doi:10.1016/j.fuproc.2022.107474.
- [24] Civancik-Uslu D, Nhu TT, Van Gorp B, Kresovic U, Larrain M, Billen P, et al. Moving from linear to circular household plastic packaging in Belgium: prospective life cycle assessment of mechanical and thermochemical recycling. *Resour Conserv Recycling* 2021;171:105633. doi:10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105633.
- [25] Kusenberg M, Zayoud A, Roosen M, Thi HD, Abbas-Abadi MS, Eschenbacher A, et al. A comprehensive experimental investigation of plastic waste pyrolysis oil quality and its dependence on the plastic waste composition. *Fuel Process Technol* 2022;227:107090. doi:10.1016/j.fuproc.2021.107090.
- [26] Jeswani H, Krüger C, Russ M, Horlacher M, Antony F, Hann S, et al. Life cycle environmental impacts of chemical recycling via pyrolysis of mixed plastic waste in comparison with mechanical recycling and energy recovery. *Sci Total Environ* 2021;769:144483. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144483. PMID:33486181
- [27] Schwarz AE, Ligthart TN, Godoi Bizarro D, De Wild P, Vreugdenhil B, van Harmelen T. Plastic recycling in a circular economy; determining environmental performance through an LCA matrix model approach. *Waste Manag* 2021;121:331–42. doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2020.12.020. PMID:33412464
- [28] Uekert T, Singh A, DesVeaux JS, Ghosh T, Bhatt A, Yadav G, et al. Technical, economic, and environmental comparison of closed-loop recycling technologies for common plastics. *ACS Sustain Chem Eng* 2023;11(3):965–78. doi:10.1021/acssuschemeng.2c05497.
- [29] Lange JP. Managing plastic waste—sorting, recycling, disposal, and product redesign. *ACS Sustain Chem Eng* 2021;9(47):15722–38. doi:10.1021/acssuschemeng.1c05013.
- [30] Klotz M, Oberschelp C, Salah C, Subal L, Hellweg S. The role of chemical and solvent-based recycling within a sustainable circular economy for plastics. *Sci Total Environ* 2024;906:167586. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.167586. PMID:37804985
- [31] Lange JP, Kersten SRA, De Meester S, van Eijk MCP, Ragaert K. Plastic recycling stripped naked—from circular product to circular industry with recycling cascade. *ChemSusChem* 2024;17(12):e202301320. doi:10.1002/cssc.202301320. PMID:38376153
- [32] Geyer R, Jambeck JR, Law KL. Production, use, and fate of all plastics ever made. *Sci Adv* 2017;3(7):e1700782. doi:10.1126/sciadv.1700782. PMID:28776036
- [33] Aneja S, Kalakoti S, Parihar DS. Urgent need of plastic waste management: a review. *Res Rev Int J Multidiscip* 2024;9(9):114–24. doi:10.31305/rrijm.2024.v09.n09.014.

- [34] Drzyzga O, Prieto A. Plastic waste management, a matter for the 'community'. *Microb Biotechnol* 2019;12(1):66–8. doi:10.1111/1751-7915.13328. PMID:30411497
- [35] Regulation (EU) 2025/40 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 December 2024 on packaging and packaging waste, amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 and Directive (EU) 2019/904, and repealing Directive 94/62/EC. Document 32025R0040. 2025 Jan 22.
- [36] Ragaert K, Ragot C, Van Geem KM, Kersten S, Shiran Y, De Meester S. Clarifying European terminology in plastics recycling. *Curr Opin Green Sustain Chem* 2023;44:100871. doi:10.1016/j.cogsc.2023.100871.
- [37] Antonopoulos I, Faraca G, Tonini D. Recycling of post-consumer plastic packaging waste in the EU: recovery rates, material flows, and barriers. *Waste Manag* 2021;126:694–705. doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2021.04.002. PMID:33887695
- [38] Eriksen MK, Pivnenko K, Faraca G, Boldrin A, Astrup TF. Dynamic material flow analysis of PET, PE, and PP flows in Europe: evaluation of the potential for circular economy. *Environ Sci Technol* 2020;54(24):16166–75. doi:10.1021/acs.est.0c03435. PMID:33225689
- [39] Kleinhans K, Hallemans M, Huysveld S, Thomassen G, Ragaert K, Van Geem KM, et al. Development and application of a predictive modelling approach for household packaging waste flows in sorting facilities. *Waste Manag* 2021;120:290–302. doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2020.11.056. PMID:33333467
- [40] Roosen M, Mys N, Kleinhans K, Lase IS, Huysveld S, Brouwer M, et al. Expanding the collection portfolio of plastic packaging: impact on quantity and quality of sorted plastic waste fractions. *Resour Conserv Recycling* 2022;178:106025. doi:10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.106025.
- [41] Watkins E, Romagnoli V, Kirhensteine I, Ruckley F, Kreissig J, Mitsios A, et al. Support to the Circular Plastics Alliance in establishing a work plan to develop guidelines and standards on design-for-recycling of plastic products. Saveyn H, Garbarino E, editors. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union; 2020.
- [42] Kawecki D, Scheeder PRW, Nowack B. Probabilistic material flow analysis of seven commodity plastics in Europe. *Environ Sci Technol* 2018;52(17):9874–88.
- [43] e!Sankey—show the flow [Internet]. Reutlingen: iPoint-systems GmbH; [cited 2025 Mar 21]. Available from: <https://www.ipoint-systems.com/software/e-sankey/>.
- [44] Single-use plastic beverage bottles—EU rules for calculating, verifying and reporting on recycled plastic content [Internet]. Brussels: European Commission; [cited 2025 Jul 15]. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/13467-Single-use-plastic-beverage-bottles-EU-rules-for-calculating-verifying-and-reporting-on-recycled-plastic-content_en.
- [45] ISO 14040:2006: Environmental management—life cycle assessment—principles and framework. ISO standard. Geneva: International Organization for Standardization; 2006.
- [46] Bracquené E, Dewulf W, Dufloy JR. Measuring the performance of more circular complex product supply chains. *Resour Conserv Recycling* 2020;154:104608. doi:10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.104608.
- [47] Ellen MacArthur Foundation, ANSYS Granta. An approach to measuring circularity. Isle of Wight: Ellen MacArthur Foundation; 2019.
- [48] de Vries J, de Bruyn S, Boerdijk S, Juijn D, Bijleveld M, van der Giesen C, et al. Environmental prices handbook 2024: EU27 version. Report. Delft: CE Delft; 2024.
- [49] SYSTEMIQ. ReShaping plastics: pathways to a circular, climate neutral plastics system in Europe. Report. Amsterdam: SYSTEMIQ; 2022.
- [50] Dai L, Lata S, Cobb K, Zou R, Lei H, Chen P, et al. Recent advances in polyolefinic plastic pyrolysis to produce fuels and chemicals. *J Anal Appl Pyrolysis* 2024;180:106551. doi:10.1016/j.jaap.2024.106551.
- [51] Liu T, Wang W, Yu D, Zhu X, Li J, Wang Y. Recent advances in pyrolysis upcycling of waste plastics into hydrocarbon fuels on biochar-based catalysts. *Appl Energy* 2025;391:125805. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2025.125805.
- [52] Garcia-Saravia Ortiz-de-Montellano C, Samani P, van der Meer Y. How can the circular economy support the advancement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)? A comprehensive analysis. *Sustain Prod Consum* 2023;40:352–62. doi:10.1016/j.spc.2023.07.003.
- [53] Luzzati T, Distefano T, Ialenti S, Andreoni V. The circular economy and longer product lifetime: framing the effects on working time and waste. *J Clean Prod* 2022;380(Pt 1):134836. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.134836.
- [54] Klose S, Pauliuk S. Quantifying longevity and circularity of copper for different resource efficiency policies at the material and product levels. *J Ind Ecol* 2021;25(4):979–93. doi:10.1111/jiec.13092.
- [55] Gonçalves M, Freire F, Garcia R. Material flow analysis and circularity assessment of plastic packaging: an application to Portugal. *Resour Conserv Recycling* 2024;209:107795. doi:10.1016/j.resconrec.2024.107795.

- [56] Vadoudi K, Deckers P, Demuytere C, Askanian H, Verney V. Comparing a material circularity indicator to life cycle assessment: the case of a three-layer plastic packaging. *Sustain Prod Consum* 2022;33:820–30. doi:10.1016/j.spc.2022.08.004.
- [57] Golkaram M, Mehta R, Taveau M, Schwarz A, Gankema H, Urbanus JH, et al. Quality model for recycled plastics (QMRP): an indicator for holistic and consistent quality assessment of recycled plastics using product functionality and material properties. *J Clean Prod* 2022;362:132311. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.132311.
- [58] Roosen M, Mys N, Kusenbergh M, Billen P, Dumoulin A, Dewulf J, et al. Detailed analysis of the composition of selected plastic packaging waste products and its implications for mechanical and thermochemical recycling. *Environ Sci Technol* 2020;54(20):13282–93. doi:10.1021/acs.est.0c03371. PMID:32985869
- [59] van Akker M, Strien JRJ, Genuino HC, van Eijk MCP, Schenk NJ, Heeres HJ, et al. Full utilization of hard-to-recycle mixed plastic waste by conversion toward pyrolysis oil and BTX aromatics on a pilot scale. *Energy Fuels* 2025;39(13):6438–51. doi:10.1021/acs.energyfuels.4c05631.
- [60] Crisis in EU plastic recycling demands immediate action [Internet]. Brussels: *Plastics Recyclers Europe*; 2025 Mar 19 [cited 2025 Jun 10]. Available from: <https://www.plasticsrecyclers.eu/news/crisis-in-eu-plastic-recycling-demands-immediate-action/>.